

Six resistant lines, mostly cross combinations of CR94 (CR55-36/IR8) and CR95 (Leuang 152/IR8) from the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, were tested in 1980-81 with two popular GM-

resistant varieties in a replicated randomized block design. Plot size was 30 m², spacing was 20 x 15 cm.

All GM-resistant lines showed resistance, but the susceptible check Jaya had

damage ranging from 12.8% to 17.5% silvershoots. CR94-721-3 and CR94-72-1-1 yielded more than Jaya and matured at the same time as Jaya (127-130 d) (see table). □

Rices with multiple disease and insect resistance in hilly regions of Uttar Pradesh

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Rice is the most important kharif cereal crop in the hills of UP. Several diseases and insects reduce yield. Of more than 60 rice pests recorded in this region, blast (Bl) caused by *Pyricularia oryzae*, brown spot (BS) caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae*, sheath rot (ShR) caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae*, and leaf scald (LSc) caused by *Rhynchosporium oryzae* are the most serious diseases, and stem borer (SB) *Sesamia inferens*, and leaf folder (LF) *Chaphalocrocis medinalis* are important insects. Bl and SB are the most serious pests.

Many genotypes have been evaluated for Bl resistance under heavy disease pressure at VLHA from 1977 to 1981. Several promising lines have been identified. In 1982 these lines were screened for BS resistance in artificial epiphytotic conditions. Most lines with Bl resistance have

Reactions of rice varieties with resistance to Bl, SB, and other pests in UP.

Cultivar	Reaction							
	Artificial epiphytotic conditions			Field conditions				
	Bl	Neck Bl	BS	ShR	LSc	SB	LF	
Dissi hatif (73127)	1	1	6	1	3	1	1	
Tetep	0	1	5	3	3	1	1	
VL-8	3	1	6	3	3	1	3	
IR9202-21-1	2	1	8	3	3	3	3	
IR3273-339-2-5	1	3	8	1	5	1	1	
IR4547-6-2-5	1	1	5	3	5	1	1	
Ta-poo-cho-z	0	1	6	3	3	1	1	
IR1416-128-5-8	2	3	7	5	3	1	1	
Milyang 46	2	3	6	3	5	1	1	
Camponi SML	1	3	8	7	3	3	3	
RP1057-35-1-1	4	3	7	3	5	3	1	
Milyang 47	3	3	8	3	5	3	1	
Colombia II	2	1	7	5	5	3	3	
IR1544-238-2-3	2	3	7	5	5	3	3	
IR5031-Plp-4B	2	3	7	5	5	3	3	
IR5908-84-2-3-3	2	3	6	7	5	1	1	
Toride 1	4	3	8	5	5	3	1	
Zenith	4	3	8	5	5	3	—	
Susceptible check ^a	9	9	9	7	7	7	5	

^aSusceptible checks were China 1039 for Bl, BS, SB, and LF; and Bala for LSc and ShR.

also been evaluated for resistance to SB in the field. Resistance levels were scored by the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice. The most important lines with multiple pest resistance are shown in the

table.

Dissi hatif (73127), Tetep, VL-8, Ta-poo-cho-z, and IR9202-21-1 had multiple resistance to the maximum number of diseases and insects. □

Varietal screening for brown planthopper resistance in China

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Rice varieties from the International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery (IRBPHN) were screened at seedling stage and in the field for resistance to brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) at Hunan Academy of Agricultural Science from

spring 1980 to fall 1982. IRBPHN experimental procedures were followed.

Of 313 rice varieties screened, 37 cultivars were resistant at the seedling stage and 53 showed resistance in the field (see table). Resistance was scored by

Varieties resistant (score 1) to the brown planthopper at seedling stage and in field tests at Changsha, Hunan, China, 1980-82.

Variety or line	Origin	Resistance ^a								Duration ^b (days)
		Seedling stage				Field				
		1980	1981	1982	AV	1980	1981	1982	AV	
ASD7	India					R ^c	R	R	R	120-128
Mudgo	India	R ^c	R	MR	R	R ^c		MR	R	135
IR46	IRRI						R ^d	MR ^d	R	NH
Rathu-Heenati	Sri Lanka	R	R	MR	R	R	R	MR	R	NH
Hondarawala	Sri Lanka	R	R	R	R	R	R		R	NH
Sinna Sivappu	Sri Lanka	R	R	MR	R	R	MR		R	NH

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Table continued.

Variety or line	Origin	Resistance ^a								Duration ^b (days)
		Seedling stage				Field				
		1980	1981	1982	AV	1980	1981	1982	AV	
BG367-9	Sri Lanka	R	MR		R	R	R		R	126-127
BG379-1	Sri Lanka	R			R	R	R		R	NH
PTB33	India	R	R	MR	R	R	R	MR	R	NH
IR13525-43-2-3-1-3-2	IRRI		R	R	R					124
IR15318-2-2-2-2	IRRI					R	R		R	NH
IR13240-39-3	IRRI					R	R	MR	R	107-132
IR13429-86-2	IRRI					R	R		R	NH
IR13540-56-3-2-1	IRRI						R	MR	R	NH
IR15529-253-3-2-2-2	IRRI						R	R	R	124
Surya Medal	Indonesia	R				R				HNR
Sudu Hondarawala	Sri Lanka					R				NH
B2980B-SR-2-1-1-1-2-1	Indonesia	R				R				137
BG367-8	Sri Lanka	R				R				137
BG379-2	Sri Lanka	R				R				HNR
BG379-3	Sri Lanka	R				R				HNR
BKnbr 1030-11-2	Thailand					R				135
BKnbr 1088-77	Thailand	R								NH
IR9209-26-2-2-2-3	IRRI	R								137
IR9224-223-2-2-2-1	IRRI	R				R				128
IR9752-1-2-1	IRRI					R				NH
IR9752-71-3-2	IRRI					R				137
IR9761-8-2	IRRI					R				137
IR9829-91-2-3	IRRI					R				137
IR13240-53-6-3-3	IRRI	R				R				137
IR13429-198-2	IRRI	R				R				128
IR13429-3-2	IRRI	R				R				138
IR13524-5-2-3-3	IRRI	R				R				NH
IR14252-13-2-2-5	IRRI	R				R				NH
IR15314-44-3	IRRI					R				HNR
IR15314-30-3-1-3	IRRI	R								HNR
IR15315-43-1	IRRI	R				R				NH
IR15496-219-2-3	IRRI	R				R				NH
IR15539-37-2-2	IRRI	R				R				HNR
IR17491-5-4-3-3	IRRI					R				HNR
IR17492-17-12-2	IRRI	R				R				HNR
IR17492-18-10-2-2-2	IRRI	R				R				HNR
IR17492-32-3-1-1-3	IRRI	R				R				NH
IR17494-32-3-4	IRRI	R								NH
IR17496-2-25-1	IRRI	R								NH
IR19657-87-3-3	IRRI	R								NH
IR19661-13-3-2	IRRI	R				R				NH
IR19670-177-1	IRRI	R				R				NH
KAU10666	IRRI	R				R				116
ARC6650	India					R				NH
Karuhondarawala	Sri Lanka					R		R		NH
Sudurusamba	Sri Lanka		R					R		NH
PTb19	India		R					R		NH
Cheng Cheongbyeo	Korea								R	121
Mudukiriyal	Sri Lanka								R	NH
B27916-Mr-257-3-2	Indonesia								R	NH
Chianung sen yu13	Taiwan, China								R	124
IR13429-196-1	IRRI								R	118
IR19791-12-1-2-2-2	IRRI								R	118
M61b-118-4-1	Indonesia			R						NH
M61b-5-1-1	Indonesia								R	NH

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant. ^bNH = not heading, HNR = heading, not ripe. ^cb = av of 3 replications. ^d = av of 4 replications.

the Standard Evaluation System for Rice. Some scores were averaged over 3 years. Among the resistant varieties were cul-

tivars from India, Sri Lanka, Indonesia, Thailand, IRRI, Taiwan, China, Japan, Burma, Malaya, Malagasy, and Pakistan.

Mudgo, BG367-8, and BG367-9 have suitable characteristics and are being used in the breeding program. □

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